

Socio-Economic Empowerment of Women through Self-Help Groups in Ganjam District of Odisha

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Abstract

This paper focused on the Socio-economic empowerment of women through Self Help Groups. Women empowerment is one of the vital issues in which women challenge the existing norms and culture, to effectively promote they're well being. The Self Help Groups made a significant impact on their empowerment economic aspects. This study addresses women empowerment through self-help groups in the Ganjam District of Odisha state. The Self-help group is a village-based financial committee usually composed of 10-20 local women or men. In India, many self-help groups are links to banks for the delivery of Micro-Credit. Women's empowerment has become a significant topic of discussion in development and economics. The objective of this paper highlights the important issues and challenges of socio-economic empowerment women through SHGs in the Ganjam district of Odisha. Empowerment of women is one of the most important issues of development. SHGs have become an important movement in India. It is a well-known fact that the growth of women, in turn, develops her family, village and, the nation in general. In the past days, women were not to take part any work and job due to shyness and male dominance in the society. But latter, Indian women have come out of the four walls of the kitchen and shown their willingness to take up entrepreneurial activities. This study is focused on primary and secondary sources of data and taken some case studies. The results of the study pointed out that the SHGs had a greater impact on the economic aspects of the beneficiaries.

Keywords: women empowerment, Self Help Groups, Micro- Credit, entrepreneurial activity.

Introduction

The government of India has launched and implemented several schemes towards poverty alleviation and women empowerment. This led to the country to launch a mother program could Swarna Jayanti Yojana(SJY) which was based on a group approach. Women in rural India are forced to play a very subordinate status to their male counterparts both at home and outside, and the wages that they receive for their work are much lesser as compared to their male counterparts. Further, they are either compelled to work within the confines of the household and if they are working outside, they are generally engaged in low-paid field activities which do little to enhance their self-esteem and socio-economic status. SHG is a group of rural poor females who have volunteered to organize themselves

into a group for the eradication of poverty of the members. They agree to save regularly and convert their savings into a common fund known as the Group corpus. The members of the group agree to use this common fund as a group through common management.

Women empowerment through Self Help Groups constitutes an emerging and first growing trend towards social, and economic development of the nation. Self Help Groups are one of the innovative and much-needed schemes to accelerate the women entrepreneurship, women's self-employment and women empowerment.

Role of the Government of India in Women Empowerment

The initial few plans followed a welfares approach and treated women as recipients of aid. The first five-year plan focused its attention on the problem of high infant. The Second plan was on the problems of women workers. The main thrust of the third and fourth plan was the expansion of girls' education. On the social welfare side, the largest share was provided for expanding rural welfare services and condensed courses of education for adult women. The fifth plan gave priority for the training of women with dependent children and working women. The sixth plan emphasis on women and development through economic independence, educational advancement and access to health care and family planning.

How to Develop Women Entrepreneurs

1. The Government should extend better educational facilities o women.
2. Training on professional competence and leadership skill should extended to women entrepreneurs.
3. Women's participation in decision making should be encouraged.
4. The Government should come up with more schemes to motivate women entrepreneurs to engage in small scale and large scale business ventures.

Socio-Economic Empowerment of Women

Women represented 50% of the world population, of which 50% forms the official labor force, 60% of the total working hours will be performed by women but received only 10% of world's income. This is the economic profile of women in the world. This is also true of India women and very much true of rural women. At this movement, macroeconomic policies and poverty eradication, programmers will especially address the needs and problems of such women.

Statement of the Problem

Self-help Groups or thrift and credit groups are mostly informal groups whose members pool savings and re-lend within the group on rotational or needs basis. Women self help groups, formed exclusively for rural women, being an effective medium for alleviating rural poverty through the empowerment of women, by freeing themselves from the clutches of usurious moneylenders. A few research works on Self Help Group have been done in Ganjam District. This research work is concerned with the exploration of SHGs and their role in making women politically, socially and economically strengthened.

Review of Literature

Hunt, J & Kasynathan, N (2002) says that microfinance has a positive impact on women's mobility and helps in reducing domestic violence. They observed that women need only a small opportunity to build their pathway to empowerment. Access to credit and peer support has enabled them to increase their power and decision making capacities in their households.

V.V. Desai (2011) in his study, says that the enhancement of entrepreneurship qualities among the members of Self Help Groups is a significant step towards social and economic empowerment of women. His suggestions for improvements are the development of a skill-oriented training program, encouragement of good leadership in the group and constant guidance and support through the government's organizations.

Objectives

1. To identify the profile of the respondents.
2. To identify the nature and extent of the group-related and personal problems faced by the members of SHGs.
3. To analyze the economic gains derived from the members after joining the SHGs.
4. To analyze the role of Government NGOs, MFIs, and different Banks towards Self Help Groups.

Research Methodology

The present study predominantly exploratory one. It is based on both primary data and secondary data. The primary data were collected from the sample of 250 women members of SHG belonging to rural Ganjam District selected on a random sampling basis. In this study, primary data were collected from directly respondents by pre-designed questionnaire. The secondary sources include different books, journals, magazines, newspapers, reports, and different governmental and non-governmental publications.

Table 1

Age	Percentage
Less than 20	13
20 to 40	34
40 to 60	42
60 to above	11
Total	100

Table 1 refers the distribution of sample of respondents by age. It is found that 13 % of the respondents are in the age of less than 20 and 34 % of respondents are the age of 20 to 40, and 42% of respondents are in between the age of 40 to 60, and 11% of respondents are between the age of 60 to above.

Table 2

Occupation	Percentage
Agriculture	50
Caste-based service	30
Others	20
Total	100

Table 2 shows the distribution of sample respondents by their occupation. It is observed that 50% of the respondents are involved in agriculture, followed by 30% are involved in caste- based services and, 20% are involved in other sources. Thus, the occupation of most of the respondents is agriculture.

Table 3

Decision making	Agriculture	Other Activities
Increase	50	63
Constant	50	37
Total	100	100

Table-3 shows that, the distribution of respondents by decision making. It is pointed out that 50% of respondents are increased decision making in agriculture, and 50% of respondents are constant in agriculture. 63% of respondents are increased their decision making in agriculture, and 37% of respondents are constant in agriculture.

Table 4

Reasons for joining	Percentage
To supplement family income	14
To cause women empowerment	47
For community development	21
More suitable for women	18
Total	100

Table-4 refers to the distribution of respondents by reason for joining. It reveals that 14% of respondents joining in Self-help groups to supplement family income, and 47% for to cause women empowerment, and 21% for community development, and 18% more suitable for women.

Conclusion

Women as a group can establish their identity and face any challenges in their lives. Women in India are victims of a multiple socio-economic factors. The role of women in the development of the nation is equally important as man. Women's empowerment is essential for our society. Education empowers women to make choices that can improve their welfare. Empowerment acts as a powerful tool against exploitation faced by women.

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